

Doping effects on the tribological performance of diamond-like carbon coatings: A review

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ABSTRACT

Diamond-like carbon (DLC) coatings have garnered considerable interest due to their unique features, which include wear resistance with a low friction coefficient, high hardness, biocompatibility, and chemical inertness. Their tribological performance is highly dependent on tribological environment, structure, and mechanical properties of the coating. A major problem that can adversely impact the tribological properties of the DLC coating is insufficient adhesion to the substrate. This issue caused by mismatch of the substrate and coating thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) and high amount of internal stress in DLC coating. The limitations of DLC coatings for tribological performance can be overcome by incorporating different types of metallic and non-metallic elements into the coating structure. Recently, various efforts have been made to address this issue by doping certain elements into the DLC coating, including fluorine, nitrogen, silicon, and metals. This review discusses new advancements in doped DLC coatings designed to improve their tribological behavior in different specific applications such as high relative humidity, elevated temperature, and bio-implant.

1. Introduction

Tribological contacts account for 25 % of global energy consumption, having a significant impact on both the economy and the environment. Finding suitable approaches to reduce tribological damage is thus a primary focus of many researchers [1]. Fabricating wear-resistant coatings is appealing as a solution to reduce the cost of tribology losses [2]. There is a huge industrial demand for improved tribological coatings to enhance the mechanical component performance by reducing wear damage and friction. In particular, solid lubricant coatings are widely applied in industries to improve the durability of machine components, particularly in clean environments and high-temperature environments, where fluid lubricants cannot be used. DLC coatings are commonly employed in mechanical components such as bearings, gears, and other components due to their superior tribological properties. These amorphous carbon-based coatings exhibit high wear resistance, chemical inertness, low coefficient of friction, and high hardness [3]. DLC coatings thus have numerous applications in biomaterials [4], corrosion protection [5], electronics, and optics [6–9].

DLC coatings are categorized into two main groups: hydrogenated

[10] and non-hydrogenated [11,12], with different types of techniques being applied to fabricate them [13]. Their tribological performance is strongly dependent on the coating's structure and the experimental conditions, which include contact pressure, speed, environment and temperature [14]. The coating nature mainly depends on the processing parameters prepared through chemical vapor deposition (CVD) or physical vapor deposition (PVD) techniques [15,16]. The hydrogenated DLC coatings can be fabricated using CVD methods such as radio frequency plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition (RF-PECVD) [17, 18] and plasma assisted chemical vapor deposition (PACVD) [19,20]. Non-hydrogenated DLC coatings are fabricated by different types of PVD processes such as magnetron sputtering [21], mass-selected ion beam (MSIB) [22] and filter cathodic vacuum arc (FCVA) [23] techniques. The hydrogenated DLC coating can be degraded at high temperatures into graphite, which can increase the wear rate [24,25]. Non-hydrogenated DLC coatings show better resistance to oxidation at elevated temperatures [26].

Generally, there are many factors that can influence the tribological behavior of DLC coatings. For instance, adhesion of the coating to the substrate [27], hardness [28], tribological environment [29], elastic

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modulus [30], surface roughness [9], and chemical structure and composition [31] are the most important factors in tribological behavior. Additionally, a DLC coating with different sp^3/sp^2 ratios of carbon hybridization can be achieved using different methods and adjusting the process parameters [32]. Relative humidity, vacuum conditions, and presence of oxygen in the environment give rise to the formation of compounds characteristic by high friction coefficient, which can increase the wear rate and friction coefficient of the coating [6,33,34].

One of the most challenging issues in DLC coatings is the high amount of residual stress due to thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) mismatch between the coating and substrate. The accumulation of high residual stress is a major drawback for the fabrication of DLC coating because it restricts the film thickness. The formation of micro strain within the amorphous matrix of DLC film leads to residual compressive stress, which causes delamination of the coating.

Several approaches have been applied to reduce the internal stress in DLC coatings, such as applying an interlayer between the substrate and coating, or surface treatment before deposition. Implementation of the graded inter-layers homogenizes the stress distribution, which enhances adhesion to the substrate. These treatments are used to increase the substrate hardness and to modify the TEC mismatch between the coating and the substrate [35,36]. The approach to reducing the residual stress associated with TEC mismatch between the substrate and coating is to apply silicon carbide, or chromium oxide as an interface layer [23,37], multilayers with different intrinsic mechanical properties, and plasma nitriding surface treatment to increase the substrate hardness [38,39].

Stress reduction is possible also through the incorporation of some metallic elements such as Ni [40], Ti [41], Al [42], and Cr [43] and some non-metallic elements such as Si [44], F [45], and N [46] into the DLC coatings. Doping with these elements can influence the structure of the DLC coatings, particularly the sp^3/sp^2 ratio. For instance, the addition of F or Si to the DLC coatings increases the water contact angle associated with lower surface energy, whereas the addition of O or N can enhance the surface energy [47]. These variations, with respect to dopant addition, can directly influence the mechanical properties of the DLC coating such as residual stress and hardness, which is critical for adhesion of the coating to the substrate and, subsequently, to tribological behavior.

The choice of a suitable interlayer, multilayer structure, processing parameters, substrate preparation, and addition of dopants is crucial for improving the adhesion and requires more technical research. This review will evaluate the fundamentals and latest developments in the tribological behavior of DLC coatings incorporated with various types of non-metallic and metallic elements.

2. DLC coatings

2.1. Structural and mechanical properties

DLC coatings are primarily composed of an amorphous carbon matrix with dispersed phases such as sp^3 and sp^2 hybridized carbon with short-range order. The sp^3/sp^2 ratio can generally be altered depending on the hydrogen content in the structure or the technique used to produce the DLC coating. DLC coatings fabricated by CVD or PECVD techniques contain a considerable amount of hydrogen due to the use of hydrocarbons as precursors. However, DLC coatings fabricated by PVD techniques using solid carbon targets, contain no hydrogen in the structure [48]. Liu et al. [49] stated that the incorporation of hydrogen in the DLC structure made the sp^3 bonds more stable. In general, the coatings produced by the sputtering technique have a high amount of sp^2 carbon bonds, whereas the coatings deposited by pulsed laser deposition contain a high amount of sp^3 carbon bonds [50].

The mechanical behavior of DLC coatings can be significantly altered by the sp^3/sp^2 ratio. The sp^3 carbon hybridization is distinguished by having the longest carbon bond lengths, which makes the coating more compact [51,52]. Sharifahmadian et al. [53] investigated the refractive

index of the carbon-based coatings with varying sp^3/sp^2 ratios. The film with the highest sp^3 content had the highest refractive index, indicating the maximum degree of cross-linking and densification. It implies that by increasing the proportion of sp^3 carbon bonds in the DLC coating, the internal stresses in the coating increase significantly [46]. By increasing the fraction of sp^3 hybridized carbon (>80 %) which is known as a tetra amorphous carbon (ta-C) coating, the hardness of the coating can be increased to 70–90 GPa [54].

2.2. Tribological properties

DLC coating provides excellent tribological capabilities because of its high hardness, high wear resistance and low friction coefficient [55]. Under unlubricated ambient conditions, DLC coatings have friction coefficient values less than 0.2, which is comparable to a steel-steel sliding contact with a boundary lubricant. Similarly, DLC coatings have two to three times higher wear resistance than typical TiN coatings. Normally, DLC coatings have a wear rate between 10^{-6} to 10^{-10} mm^3/Nm , which changes depending on the coating's microstructural properties. Due to the significant number of dangling bonds, ta-C coatings containing 81 % of sp^3 hybridized carbon have a minimal coefficient of friction under lubricated conditions [56]. Furthermore, during low-temperature operations, ta-C coatings show relatively stable tribological behavior. However, at high temperatures (>200 °C), many cracks occur, which cause the coating to delaminate [57].

Understanding the tribological response of the DLC coating under unlubricated conditions, such as forming tribofilm, can provide valuable information for achieving better tribological behavior of the coating. During sliding in dry conditions between a counterpart and the DLC coating surface, a unique carbon-rich tribolayer can be formed. This tribolayer has a positive influence on tribological behavior, enabling it to overcome fluctuations in the friction coefficient and decrease the wear rate of the DLC coating. However, this tribolayer sometimes causes abrasive wear due to the formation of hard wear debris particles. Therefore, the creation and growth of the tribolayer are attributed to the chemical and mechanical properties of the counterparts, and particularly wear test conditions, such as humidity, temperature, oxidative reactant, and lubrication [2,58,59].

2.3. Influence of hydrogen on tribological properties

The tribological properties of the DLC coatings in various environmental circumstances are significantly impacted by the incorporation of hydrogen in the coating. Basically, the non-hydrogenated DLC coatings have greater friction coefficient than the hydrogenated DLC coatings in inert environments. However, in ambient conditions, friction coefficient of hydrogenated DLC coating increases, but that of non-hydrogenated DLC coating is shown to significantly decrease [60].

The non-hydrogenated DLC coated surface interactions for different sliding situations are schematically represented in Fig. 1. With increasing humidity and temperature, graphitization occurs under sliding conditions, and chemical reactions can occur, resulting in the creation of C–O–O, C–O, and C–OH bonds. The friction coefficient was found to be reduced by such tribo-chemical layers [61]. However, such surface contact cannot be passivated by environmental species in an inert environment. As a result, friction coefficient increases in an inert environment due to higher fresh C–C bonds on the surface [62].

However, for hydrogenated DLC coating, tribo-chemical interactions between solid surfaces are mostly determined by the presence of hydrogen. A significant reduction in coating friction is achieved by the hydrogen-bonded molecules on the surface of the DLC coatings, which essentially prohibit C–C bonding at the interface of friction [63]. Carbon bonds terminated with hydrogen atoms on the surface (Fig. 1) of hydrogenated DLC coatings, promote weaker surface contacts and reduce contact stress significantly. Di-hydrated carbon atoms are carbon atoms that sometimes have two hydrogen atoms bonded to them. One carbon

(a) DLC / DLC coated surfaces

Fig. 1. Schematic of tribological performance of H-free and H-DLC coatings as a function of humidity and temperature. (a) H-free DLC/DLC-coated surface interactions; (b) H-DLC/H-DLC-coated surface interactions [63].

atom can be attached to two hydrogen atoms; this is known as a di-hydrated carbon atom. The higher degree of passivation provided by these di-hydrated carbon atoms on the DLC surface. Thus, the removal of the strong covalent C–C bond and the potential for producing di-hydrated carbon in the interface of the DLC are the primary causes of the super lubricity of hydrogenated DLC [64]. However, chemical reactions occur under high operating temperatures, and high humidity level. In other words, due to the absorbance of the water molecules on the surface, capillary forces increase around the contact area resulting in an increase in the friction coefficient [62].

Costa et al. [65] fabricated H-DLC coatings using HiPIMS-DOMS technique by employing various Ar/CH₄ ratios. They demonstrated that by raising the hydrogen content, the coefficient of friction reduces from 0.15 to 0.10. But as a result of less hardness of the coatings by increasing the hydrogen content, the wear rate of the H-DLC coating increases. In another study, Mobarak et al. investigated the tribological behavior of hydrogenated and non-hydrogenated DLC coatings. In contrast to non-hydrogenated coating, H-DLC coating cannot provide wear protection at high temperatures. Because tribochemical layers preferentially cannot be formed on the counter surface of H-DLC coating. Manimunda et al. [66] reported the coefficient of friction of the heat treated H-DLC coatings decreased from 0.2 to 0.08. It appears that the subsurface hydrogen loss was stopped by an oxide layer formed

during air annealing. Therefore, at the oxide/H-DLC interface, sp³ carbon atoms were produced by the interaction of released hydrogen with sp² carbon atoms. According to Solis et al. [67], H-DLC coatings produced by a PECVD process reduce wear and friction as the applied load increases from 10 to 50 N while testing without lubrication. According to the theory, the H atoms may be expelled from the matrix, resulting in hydrogen deficient sites in the friction interface [68]. As a result, the Hertzian contact pressure rises and graphitization rate is increased, favoring the change of sp³ bound carbons to sp² graphitic carbons. Apart from hydrogen content, sp³/sp² ratio and dopant concentrations, several other extrinsic and intrinsic factors influence the wear and friction behavior of DLC and H-DLC coatings. Surface roughness, microstructure, operating temperature, and sliding environments are only a few of the primary elements that determine tribological properties of the DLC coatings [65].

2.4. Improvement of coating adhesion

The most common issues with DLC coatings include a mismatch in the coefficient of thermal expansion between substrate and film, as well as internal stress in the coatings. Each of these problems may affect how well the coating adheres to the substrate, influencing the tribological behavior. This issue can be fixed by applying suitable inter-layers (called

seed layers) over the substrates to deposit thick and more adherent DLC coatings. For instance, ceramic interlayers of SiC, Si₃N₄, CrN, TiN and TiC have been deposited on different substrates [69,70]. By applying DLC coating on AISI 316L stainless steel, the tribocorrosion properties can also be improved using a suitable sub-layer of a-SiNx:H between the coating and the substrate [71]. Another extremely promising method for enhancing the adhesion of the DLC coating to the substrate is plasma nitriding [72]. By forming metal nitride compounds at a certain depth of the substrate surface, the surface hardness of the substrate can be increased [73–75]. This can have an influence on the reduction of residual stress in the subsequent DLC coatings [76]. In addition, this diffusion layer is a kind of passive layer which increases the corrosion resistance of some alloys, such as steels, CoCrMo alloys, and even stainless steels [77]. Recently, a DLC coating was deposited on plasma nitrided AISI 4140 steel, showing that the load bearing capacity and wear resistance of AISI 4140 steels can be improved considerably. Before deposition, plasma nitriding was applied to the substrate which improved the adhesion of the DLC coating to the substrate [78]. The schematic of the tribological behavior of the plasma-nitrided DLC coating is shown in Fig. 2.

2.5. Summary

All in all, DLC coatings with high content of sp² hybridization show low wear resistance due to low crack resistance at high contact pressure. Therefore, most researchers have taken steps to increase the hardness of DLC coating by adjusting the process parameters to achieve high content of sp³ hybridized carbon. In other words, because of the low fracture toughness, some third hard bodies created during the wear test can cause severe wear. Therefore, the primary objective of the recent research on doped or alloyed DLC coatings is to alter the microstructure and surface properties to overcome tribological limitations. This could be accomplished by lowering the residual stress and thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between the substrate and coating.

3. Fluorine-doped DLC coatings

3.1. Structural and mechanical properties

Fluorine has a significant impact on the structure of DLC coatings. Fluorine, as a highly electronegative atom, can form only a single bond with carbon and cannot prevent the formation of –C=C– bonds. Moreover, the formed C–F bonds can reduce the length of chains and rings in

the DLC structure by sticking out of the carbon network [79]. Therefore, by introducing fluorine atoms to the DLC coating, the amount of sp³ carbon hybridizations can be reduced significantly and more extensive graphitization can occur. By doping fluorine into the DLC structure, many –CF₂ and –CF₃ groups are formed in the network, which can decrease the amount of hydrogenated carbon compounds [80].

By reducing the sp³/sp² ratio in the DLC coatings due to fluorine incorporation, Young's modulus and hardness are reduced. The highest hardness reduction was reported from 14 GPa to 2 GPa by Bendavid et al. [81], whereas the lowest hardness decreases from 18.75 GPa to 16.25 GPa was reported by Agostino et al. [82]. As a result of sp³ collapse in the DLC structure, the cross-linking of carbon network decreases, making the coating less dense and compact. Therefore, by incorporating fluorine into the DLC coating, the amount of residual stress can also decrease, and adhesion strength increases [83]. Regardless of the mechanical properties, fluorine has a significant influence on the reduction of surface energy of the DLC coatings. Fluorine can reduce the dispersive component of the surface free energy of the DLC coating significantly [84]. Butter et al. fabricated a hydrophobic F-DLC coating by creating CF₂ and CF₃ groups on the surface. They found that association of sp³ carbon bonds with CF groups can create superhydrophobic surfaces [85]. Hence, one of the most important advantages of fluorine-doped DLC coatings is their adequate adhesion strength along with a low surface energy. These features can have a significant effect on the tribological behavior of the coating.

3.2. Tribological behavior at high relative humidity

The hydrophobic nature of the fluorine-doped DLC coating can provide a low friction coefficient at high relative humidity [86,87]. Bhowmick et al. [88] showed by atomistic simulations that the higher interfacial force needed to bring fluorine and OH molecules together compared to H and OH makes the F-DLC coating more hydrophobic. Liu et al. [84] reported the fabrication of a robust superhydrophobic F-DLC coating on stainless steel. In this study, a Cr/CrC/DLC/F-DLC multilayered coating was designed to improve the wear resistance and anti-icing properties of nose cones on plane engines. The multilayered coating examined in a harsh environment showed that ice formation on the coating decreased substantially. Moreover, excellent tribo-corrosion properties were observed due to easy roll-off of droplets from the surface (stable surface contact angle >150°). Due to the low friction coefficient of the fluorine-doped DLC coatings at high relative humidity, they can be excellent candidates for bio-tribology applications of

Fig. 2. Schematic of the tribological behavior of the DLC coating deposited on a) plasma nitrided and b) non-nitrided substrate during the ball on disk test.

implants used under abrasive conditions in the human body [89,90]. The F-DLC coating can reduce bacterial attachment and, due to its low surface energy, improve antithrombogenicity [91]. Additionally, by doping fluorine into the DLC coating, a fluorine-terminated surface can create higher repulsive forces during the sliding process than a fluorine-free DLC coating. These fluorinated surfaces can lower friction coefficient (0.09–0.14) of F-DLC coatings in mutual sliding conditions, even in the environment of the human body [92].

3.3. Tribological behavior at low relative humidity

Despite the excellent performance of F-DLC coatings under high relative humidity conditions, other studies have also been conducted on the use of these coatings in environments with a low relative humidity. Wang et al. [31] showed that an F-DLC coating fabricated by hollow cathode plasma immersion ion implantation has reduced Young's modulus and hardness, whereas surface roughness increased. By incorporating fluorine into the DLC film, the H/E value of 0.107 was achieved, leading to a low friction coefficient with sufficient adhesion strength. The F-DLC coating with low fluorine concentration (3.2 at. % F) showed a low wear rate and a super-low friction coefficient due to the lower surface roughness (Fig. 3). The low fluorine concentration F-DLC coating formed transfer layers of fluorine-passivated carbonaceous compounds in sliding contact with an aluminum alloy. By forming this transfer layer between the aluminum pin and F-DLC coating in a pin-on-disc wear test arrangement, the friction coefficient was reduced to 0.14.

Sen et al. [94] fabricated hydrogenated DLC coatings with an atomic concentration of fluorine between 2 % and 35 % by PECVD technique. They showed that these coatings can form stable surface thermodynamic compounds such as AlF_3 when worn against an aluminum ball. The fluorine-doped DLC coatings indicated more effective anti-sticking features in comparison with hydrogenated DLC coatings [93]. Hakovirta et al. [95] carried out wear test on fluorine-doped DLC coatings (19.7 at. % F) showing a lower friction coefficient (0.10) than the Teflon coating (0.13). Prioli et al. [96] used an atomic force microscope to evaluate the tribological properties of fluorinated DLC coatings (35 at. % F) against a Si_3N_4 ball. They were able to decrease the friction coefficient of the F-DLC to 0.16, whereas a friction coefficient of 0.21 was measured for fluorine-free DLC coatings.

3.4. Summary

In summary, the incorporation of fluorine into the DLC structure can improve the surface hydrophobicity as well as adhesion strength due to lower stress accumulation in the coating. The fluorination can be

controlled by the deposition process. Fluorination can happen by reactive species at the surface, and it most likely happens when bonded hydrogen is replaced by fluorine. The fluorine replacement can be achieved by adding a fluorocarbon, such CF_4 or CHF_3 , to a hydrocarbon plasma while DLC is being deposited. Fluorination can be boosted by greater bombardment energy, such as when a greater bias voltage is applied, or argon is added to the gas mixture. Highly fluorinated DLC coatings are soft and have a poor wear resistance, whereas F-DLC coating with low fluorine concentrations show low friction coefficients and high wear resistance that is comparable to those of pure DLC coatings without any dopant. At a high relative humidity, the F-DLC coatings show a low friction coefficient, making them applicable for tools for aqueous machining, particularly in sliding applications of the AZ91 alloy [97]. Effective anti-sticking features of the F-DLC films in sliding contact make them a suitable material in molds for nano-imprinting of polymers. The tribological properties of some F-DLC coatings, produced by various techniques, are listed in Table 1. Their structural changes, chemical composition, and mechanical properties are also reviewed.

4. Silicon-doped DLC coatings

4.1. Structural and mechanical properties

To improve the mechanical properties, tribological behavior, corrosion resistance, and thermal stability of the DLC films, several studies aimed at the incorporating of silicon into the structure. Understanding of how silicon incorporation affects the structure of DLC coatings is vital for tailoring the properties of the Si-DLC coatings. Si doping can significantly alter the microstructure of DLC films because Si-C bonds in hydrogenated DLC films are significantly longer than C-C bonds, allowing Si-doped DLC films to accommodate greater structural disorder [105]. It has been proposed that the sp^2 carbon bonds break due to silicon incorporation. At the same time an increase in carbon structure disorder increases the chance of sp^3 carbon bonds formation. With an increase in silicon content in the DLC coating, the average size of sp^2 -bonded clusters can decrease, and the sp^3 carbon bonds fraction increases [26]. An increase in sp^3/sp^2 bonds of the Si-DLC coating with increasing silicon content was indicated in some studies by a decrease in the G-band wavenumber in Raman spectra of the coatings [106,107].

Generally, DLC coatings with a high amount of sp^3 carbon bonds are characteristic by their higher hardness [108]. The mechanical behavior of the films depends on the specific material bonding properties, particularly on the hydrogenation of the sp^3 carbon-bonded matrix. Although the hydrogenated Si-DLC coatings contain more sp^3 carbon bonds than DLC coatings, their hardness is not higher due to the high

Fig. 3. (a) Friction coefficient and (b) wear rate of fluorine-doped DLC coating versus various fluorine concentrations in ambient air [93].

Table 1
Tribological behavior and some other characteristics of fluorine-doped DLC coatings.

Chemical composition/ Microstructure	Deposition technique/ Substrate	Surface roughness/ thickness (t)	Mechanical Properties	Wear test conditions	Tribological properties	Major Outcome	Ref.
0 at.%, 22 at.%, 25 at. % 41 at.%, and 45 at.% of F/lower sp ³ /sp ² after F incorporation	non-thermal atmospheric jet plasma-polymerization/ Glass	t: 98 nm RMS: 23 nm for 22 at.% of F	–	Counterpart: Steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 1 N Environment: dry	W = 2.3×10^{-8} mm ³ /Nm For 22 at.% of F	The amines in APTES improve the adhesion of fluorinated compounds to the substrate, which can increase the wear resistance of the coating.	[98]
4.8 at.%, 5.9 at.%, 6.8 at.%, 12.1 at.%, and 15.5 at.% of F/lower sp ³ /sp ² after F incorporation	PECVD/Si wafers	–	H: 17.25 GPa E: 148.6 GPa For 4.5 at.% of F	Counterpart: Al ₂ O ₃ Geometry: ball on disk Load: 6 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.06$ W = 3×10^{-15} mm ³ /Nm For 4.5 at.% of F	The friction coefficient of an F-DLC film in an inert atmosphere is lower than in the air. Since the production of C-phase as tribofilms can reduce friction and prevent tribo-oxidation.	[99]
34.59 at.% of F/lower sp ³ /sp ² after F incorporation	high-power impulse magnetron sputtering/ Stainless Steel	t = 1.5 μ m	H: 13.5 GPa E: 104 GPa	Counterpart: Stainless Steel multi-function tribometer Geometry: Load: 10 N, and cycle of 10,000 times Environment: dry	The contact angle immediately decreases in the first 3000 cycles then stabilizes at or above 130.0° even after 10,000 cycles, demonstrating the exceptional wear resistance.	Following a wear test, the coating's surface is covered with C and F, which maintains the coating's low surface energy and offers long-lasting hydrophobicity.	[100]
0, 6.5, and 19 at. % of F, lower sp ³ /sp ² after F incorporation	RF-PECVD/Steel	Ra: 20 nm t: 1.5 μ m For 6.5 at.% of F	H: 29 GPa For 6.5 at.% of F	Counterpart: Steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 10 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.04$ W = 2×10^{-8} mm ³ /Nm For 6.5 at.% of F	The F-DLC coating showed a good balance between the residual stress, and surface passivation of the coating with high surface energy compounds	[101]
lower sp ³ /sp ² after F incorporation	RF-PECVD/ Ti6Al4V	t: 229 nm	H: 6.5 GPa E: 87 GPa For highest CF ₄ Flow rate (25 sccm)	Counterpart: single-crystal diamond Berkovich Geometry: nano scratch test Load: length of 500 μ m, and loading rate of 0.04 mN/ μ m Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.2$ For highest CF ₄ Flow rate (25 sccm)	The adhesion strength of the coating decreases by adding more fluorine into the coating, despite the reduced friction coefficient	[102]
tetrahedral fluorinated amorphous carbon (ta-C-F) coating	pulsed vacuum-arc plasma technique/ WC-Co	t: 2.45 μ m for ta-C-F	H: 6 GPa E: 170 GPa for ta-C-F	Counterpart: 319 Al alloy Geometry: Pin on disk Load: 5 N Environment: Dry & high temperature	$\mu = 0.13$ W = 1×10^{-5} mm ³ /Nm for ta-C-F at 400 °C	The lower friction coefficient of ta-C-F at high temperatures compared to ta-C was caused by formation of the passivated sp ² fluorocarbons as a transfer layer	[103]
12 at.% of F	PECVD/Steel	t: 2.3 μ m	H: 8.7 GPa E: 77.2 GPa	Counterpart: Al Geometry: Ball on disk Load: 1 & 5 N Environment: Dry	$\mu = 0.1$	Due to the presence of fluorine and hydrogen, the coating surfaces become more passivated, which also contributed to the COF being reduced.	[104]

hydrogen content [106]. Due to the increased density of voids at increased Si concentration, the hardness of the Si-DLC coatings can also be reduced. On the other hand, the Si-DLC films have significantly lower internal stress than pure DLC films as a result of relaxation of highly distorted bond angles [109,110]. Hence, with the addition of silicon, the DLC coating's adhesion to the substrate can be improved, which is crucial in enhancing the tribological performance of the coating.

4.2. Tribological properties at room temperature

Several researchers concluded that silicon incorporation into the DLC network could have a positive influence on tribological properties [111,112]. In non-lubricated conditions, silicon-doped diamond-like carbon coatings can exhibit reduced friction coefficient compared to undoped DLC coating [44,113,114]. A smooth hydrogenated Si-DLC coating was fabricated using the RF-PECVD technique in a gas mixture

containing SiH₄ and acetylene. The results revealed that the amount of SiH₄ in the plasma atmosphere has only a small influence on surface roughness. The functionalized surface, with surface roughness in nanometer range, indicated a low wear rate and friction coefficient, which is suitable for orthopedic implants [115]. Ban et al. [116] deposited a hydrogenated Si-DLC coating by electron beam excited plasma (EBEP). They showed that wear scars on the Si-DLC coating contain additional oxygen components compared with the pure DLC coating. By combining PECVD with magnetron sputtering technique, it is possible to deposit a hydrogenated Si-DLC coating with a low friction coefficient of 0.005 (Fig. 4) [117]. The low shear strength of the transfer layer that forms on the sliding surface may be the cause of the low friction coefficient. In several studies, the influence of hydrogen concentration in the coating on the tribological properties of silicon-doped DLC coating has been reported [118]. Lower friction coefficients can be attained after the completion of a running-in process by increasing the

Fig. 4. Coefficient of friction of the silicon doped DLC coating sliding against Si_3N_4 ball at room temperature in ambient air environments and water [117].

hydrogen content in the hydrogenated Si-DLC coating. Moreover, silicon atoms can bond with carbon, even at low concentration; this bonding is essential at the beginning of the friction test. As claimed by Tanaka et al. [119], SiC bonds cause an initial high friction coefficient for the Si-DLC coating which is required to obtain energy for Si surface structural modifications to form transferred layers with low friction throughout the rest of the wear test. In another study, a non-hydrogenated Si-DLC coating was fabricated by Ion Beam Assisted Deposition (IBAD) on Si wafers. Hardness is increased by raising the silicon content of the Si-DLC coating and lowering the deposition temperature. It is believed that the increased SiC bonding is the cause of this behavior. Additionally, as the Si content increased, the friction coefficient of the coating changed and fell below 0.1. It is possible that low friction is caused by atmospheric moisture being adsorbed on the sliding contact to form Si–OH. On the other hand, Graphitization at low humidity and formation of the water film at high humidity are the main reasons behind the low friction of the hydrogenated Si-DLC coating [120].

4.3. Tribological properties at elevated temperature

Having inadequate wear resistance at elevated temperatures due to their degradation is a major disadvantage for the application of DLC coating. An effective way to overcome this issue is incorporation of silicon atoms into the DLC coating. Silicon can play a key role in improving the thermal stability of the coating by reducing the internal stress in the coating and simultaneously increasing the sp^3 hybridization of carbon atoms [111,121,122]. The undoped DLC coating has better tribological behavior than the Si-DLC coating below 300 °C. At temperatures ranging from 100 °C to 300 °C, hydrogen passivation and graphitization play critical roles in tribological performance of the hydrogenated carbon-based coatings. Hence, this subject has been attractive for researchers studying the tribological performance of DLC coatings at high temperatures. However, application of Si-DLC coating above 450 °C is challenging [123]. The hydrogenated Si-DLC coating maintained its lubricative properties and showed high thermal stability up to 400 °C. The friction coefficient of 0.14 was obtained at 400 °C for a hydrogenated silicon-doped DLC coating with a silicon atomic concentration of 26 % [124]. Fei et al. [125] achieved a friction coefficient value of 0.18 for the hydrogenated Si-doped DLC coating at 450 °C. Graphitization of the coating can be inhibited at elevated temperatures by incorporating silicon into the coating. The formation of Si–O–C bonds at elevated temperatures can have an additional lubrication effect during sliding. By increasing the temperature to 500 °C, silicon dioxide can be formed, causing failure of the coating. Yu et al. [126] claimed that by fabricating a composite hydrogenated Si-DLC coating with a mixture of

tungsten oxides and carbide, they could stabilize the tribological properties of the coating up to 500 °C. The silicon concentration in this DLC coating was around 5 at. %, and by reacting the tungsten interlayer with carbon and oxygen, a composite coating was fabricated which had a stable friction coefficient up to 500 °C.

4.4. Summary

Si-DLC coatings have a high wear resistance and stability of friction coefficient in ambient air and at elevated temperature in particular. As a result, the Si-DLC film is recommended as a cost-effective solid lubricant and protective coating for a variety of applications, including automotive components subjected to mild mechanical stress. Table 2 highlights the tribological properties of Si-DLC coatings fabricated by various methods. Information about their structural changes, and mechanical properties is also provided.

5. Nitrogen-doped DLC coatings

5.1. Structural and mechanical properties

The use of nitrogen as a dopant in DLC coatings to enhance their mechanical and tribological properties, as well as biocompatibility, has been the subject of several studies [46]. By introducing nitrogen into the DLC coating, its structure can be changed by forming strong bonds such as C–N, C–N–C, and C=N [133,134]. The intensity of I_D/I_G bands obtained from Raman spectra increases by rising the nitrogen content of the DLC coating. Incorporation of nitrogen into the carbon network thus encourages sp^2 carbon hybridization and subsequently reduces sp^3 carbon bonding [135–137]. Additionally, high nitrogen concentrations in the gas mixture during the PECVD process can also intensify the hydrogen cleavage from the DLC structure. Cleaved hydrogen atoms are easily replaced by nitrogen in a reactive plasma environment that is nitrogen-rich, and lower hydrogen-containing carbon structures are left behind. The mechanism behind this is supported by a rise in the CN content of the N-DLC structure, which may have a major impact on the tribological and mechanical behavior [46].

The hardness of the DLC coating can be reduced by doping nitrogen into the carbon matrix [138]. Polaki et al. [139] reported that introducing nitrogen gas into the PECVD chamber during deposition of the DLC coating on a silicon wafer can reduce the elastic modulus and hardness of the coating. In another study, the DLC coating was fabricated on a silicon substrate using RF magnetron sputtering by doping nitrogen and boron. Although the ratio of sp^3/sp^2 decreased by adding nitrogen, the hardness and toughness of the coating increased due to the formation of $-\text{C}_3\text{N}_4$ phase [140]. Most recent studies showed that by doping nitrogen from either a gaseous precursor or by sputtering (evaporation of the Si_3N_4 targets), internal stress can be reduced [141]. Kahn et al. [142] deposited N-DLC coating using magnetron sputtering and observed that the I_D/I_G bands intensity ratio obtained from Raman spectra increased as a result of incorporation of nitrogen into the DLC structure. This was attributed to the formation of C=N bonds that can reduce graphite clustering growth by pinning them in the carbon network [143]. It can be inferred that nitrogen can reduce the residual stress of the DLC coating and, consequently, help the coating adhere to the substrate more effectively.

5.2. Biotribological properties

N-DLC coating is also an interesting candidate for tribological applications because the addition of nitrogen to the DLC structure alters its mechanical properties significantly. In recent years, many studies have been focused on the tribological properties of the N-DLC coatings for implantable applications in the body environment. N-DLC coatings for bio-tribological applications were deposited by thermal CVD technique at different N_2 gas flow rates (from 70 sccm to 160 sccm) on a silicon

Table 2
Tribological behavior and some other characteristics of silicon-doped DLC coatings.

Chemical composition/ Microstructure	Deposition technique/ Substrate	Surface roughness (RMS)/ thickness (t)	Mechanical Properties	Wear test conditions	Tribological properties	Major Outcome	Ref.
5 at.% of Si/higher sp ³ / sp ² after Si incorporation	PECVD/nitrile butadiene rubber	t: 1.5 μm	–	Counterpart: WC- Co Geometry: ball on disk Load: 1,5 N Environment: dry and high humidity	μ = 0.35 W = -For 5 at.% of Si	Tribological properties are dependent on Si concentration and wear conditions	[127]
-/lower sp ³ /sp ² after Si incorporation	PECVD/nitrile butadiene rubber	–	H: 11 GPa	Counterpart: WC- Co Geometry: ball on disk Load: 5 N Environment: dry	μ = 0.3 W = -For Si- DLC film	Deposition of SiC layer increased the friction coefficient	[128]
–	PECVD/ Rubber	–	Si-DLC coated rubber has a Meyer hardness that is approximately 1.4 times greater than uncoated rubber.	Counterpart: Steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 5 N Environment: 50 % of relative humidity	μ = 0.2 W = -For Si- DLC film	Si-DLC coated rubber showed no signs of wear other than the rubber substrate's creep effect.	[129]
7.5, 10.6, 9.1, and 8.4 at. % of Si,	CVD/p-type Si	RMS: 5.6 nm t: 6.3 μm For 7.5 at.% of Si	H: 14.25 GPa E: 100.6 GPa For 7.5 at.% of Si	Counterpart: Steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 5 N Environment: dry	μ = 0.065 For 7.5 at.% of Si	The friction coefficient of the coatings rises as the C ₂ H ₂ flowrate rises, because of higher content of sp ³ bonds.	[130]
0.2 at.%, 2.6 at.%, 5.2 at. %, and 5.5 at. of Si	PVD & PECVD/ nitrile butadiene rubber	t: 1 μm for all coatings	–	Counterpart: Stainless steel & WC-Co Geometry: pin on disk Load: 1 and 5 N Environment: dry and wet	μ = 0.19 For 5.5 at.% of Si	For both dry and wet sliding conditions, the Si–C interlayer enhanced adhesion.	[131]
0 at.%, 1.25 at.%, 2.06 at. %, 3.86 at.% and 6.04 at. % of Si/Higher sp ³ / sp ² at low Si concentration	magnetron sputtering/Si (100) wafers	t: 750 nm for 1.25 at.% of Si	H: 33 GPa E: 320 GPa for 1.25 at.% of Si	Counterpart: Al ₂ O ₃ Geometry: Ball on disk Load: 5 N Environment: Dry & high temperature	μ = 0.12 W = 40 × 10 ⁻⁸ mm ³ /Nm For 1.25 at.% of Si	The coating's frictional behavior was mostly caused by formation of SiO bonds, due to the presence of low energy van der Waals interactions.	[132]
0 at.%, 4.56 at.%, 14.56 at.% of Si/higher sp ³ / sp ² after Si incorporation	IBAD/Si wafers	t: 1.4–1.8 μm	–	Counterpart: Al ₂ O ₃ Geometry: Ball on disk Load: 5 N Environment: Dry & high temperature	μ = 0.1 at 500 °C for 4.56 at. % Si	At 500 °C, the combined effect of the tungsten interlayer and amorphous carbon film lowers the friction coefficient.	[126]

wafer substrate by Ghadai et al. [144]. Enhancing the nitrogen content in the DLC coating caused an increase in surface roughness because of increased sputtering of nitrogen atoms on the surface at higher N₂ flow rates. The I_D/I_G ration obtained from Raman spectra increases by injecting more nitrogen gas into the CVD chamber, which can accelerate sp³ to sp² transformation. At a nitrogen gas flow rate of 70 sccm, a maximum hardness (25.4 GPa) and elastic modulus (180.1 GPa) were obtained; however, the elastic modulus and hardness decreased as more nitrogen gas was injected into the chamber. The nano scratch test of the N-DLC coating determined a friction coefficient of 0.04. This finding implies that N-DLC coating is a suitable candidate for bio-tribological applications [144]. One of the most widely used material combinations for artificial joint replacement is ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) combined with CoCrMo alloy. For this application, Liu et al. [145] compared the tribological properties of a

nitrogen-doped DLC coating and a non-doped DLC coating. The nitrogen-doped DLC coating showed the best tribological properties of all the samples. Abrasive wear was predominant mechanism when the soft UHMWPE slid against the N-DLC coated CoCrMo head, which led to more multidirectional scratches on the UHMWPE cup. Shiri et al. [146] fabricated a biocompatible nitrogen-doped DLC coating by incorporating diamond particles into the coating structure. The adhesion of this coating to the substrate was improved as confirmed by indentation testing. As mentioned above, nitrogen can reduce sp³ carbon bonding, and consequently the hardness and internal stress of the coating can be reduced. The wear resistance of the N-DLC coating was examined using polyethylene balls as a counterpart. The wear rate and coefficient of friction of the N-DLC coating decreased due to lower surface roughness and higher sp² bonding. The results suggested that DLC coating incorporated with diamond particles and nitrogen is an excellent option for

bio-tribological applications such as hip joints. In another study, the hydrophilicity and roughness of the hydrogenated DLC coating is enhanced by adding nitrogen to the structure. The coatings did not show any noticeably elevated cell death; nonetheless, the N-DLC coatings have superior anti-thrombotic and endothelial cell growth characteristics compared to nitrogen-free DLC coatings [147].

5.3. Tribological properties at ambient conditions

In addition to bio-tribological applications, fabricating N-DLC coatings on steel tools such as molds and dies is a promising way to extend their lifespan. These parts are frequently subjected to severe wear. Sharifahmadian et al. [148] investigated the nitrogen effect on the tribological properties and structural evolution of the DLC coating on H13 Tool Steel using the PECVD method. The XPS and Raman spectroscopy results revealed that enhancing the flow rate of nitrogen can accelerate the carbon transformation of sp^3 to sp^2 . In other words, by increasing the temperature during the deposition, the nitrogen content in the DLC coating decreases, and consequently, the sp^3 bonding increases. Either by increasing the flow rate of nitrogen while maintaining a similar deposition temperature, or by reducing the temperature while maintaining a similar flow rate of nitrogen, the hardness was reduced [149,150]. The DLC coating containing a high amount of nitrogen demonstrated stable tribological behavior. Conversely, the N-DLC coating with low nitrogen content displayed a lower friction coefficient at the beginning of the wear test [148]. However, as nitrogen concentration of the DLC coating increases, the friction coefficient of the coating becomes more stable. The high adhesion strength of the N-DLC coating allows the tribological layer to remain on the surface during the sliding process. The abrasive wear mechanism is confirmed by scratches that are formed parallel to the direction of sliding. However, due to the lower hardness and higher toughness of the N-DLC coatings compared to the pure DLC coating, the abrasive wear mechanism is not more severe. In this case, at the beginning of the wear test, the friction coefficient of the N-DLC coating is higher than that of the pure DLC coating due to reduced hardness [148,149].

The N-DLC/DLC coating was fabricated on the steel substrate using PECVD technique and the tribological behavior of the N-DLC/DLC single layer coatings was evaluated [151]. A typical schematic representation of the N-DLC/DLC coating is shown in Fig. 5. The nitrogen content from the top surface of the coating decreases towards the substrate interface, whereas the hardness increases gradually from the substrate to the surface of the coating.

After evaluation of FTIR spectra, the presence of $C \equiv N$ is confirmed in both the single- and double-layer coatings, which can reduce the interlink bonds in the carbon network. This can give rise to a decrease in hardness and release the residual stress of the coatings. The friction coefficient of the double-layer coating was more stable and even lower than that of each single-layer coating. In other words, DLC coating as the second layer is responsible for low friction behavior, and the N-DLC coating as the first layer can improve coating adhesion to the substrate, thereby making the friction coefficient of the N-DLC/DLC coating more stable. The tribological behavior of the double layer and single layer coatings is shown in Fig. 6 [151].

Fig. 5. Schematic of the graded DLC coating. The nitrogen content from coating surface decreases to the substrate, whereas the hardness increases gradually from substrate to the coating surface.

Sharifahmadian et al. [152] used the PECVD active screen method to deposit a gradient N-DLC coating. In the active screen approach, the ionization and dissociation of plasma components can be accelerated. This leads to the formation of a higher amount of sp^3 bonding in the DLC coating. Moreover, cracks were observed on the wear surface, which were perpendicular to the sliding direction. It demonstrated the wear mechanism changed from abrasive wear to fatigue. The coating delaminates as the sliding process continues. However, the active screen specimen has a significant number of cracks on its wear surface, which suggests that the wear process is being delayed. The rapid crack growth of the single layer N-DLC coating leads to a lower durability compared to the gradient coating.

5.4. Summary

Nitrogen incorporation into the DLC coatings can have a significant impact on their structure modification, mechanical, and tribological properties. Although introducing nitrogen atoms into the DLC structure reduces the coating hardness and improves the toughness, it improves coating adhesion to the substrate, resulting in higher stability in the tribological behavior of the DLC coating. The N-DLC coating has been used for a variety of applications, including surgical tools, mechanical face seals, magnetic hard discs, dies, and molds [59]. Table 3 provides a list of the mechanical and tribological properties of other N-DLC coatings deposited using different methods.

6. Metal-doped DLC coatings

6.1. Structural and mechanical properties

Metals are a type of dopant that has drawn the interest of many researchers due to their significant impact on the enhancement of the mechanical and tribological properties of the DLC coatings. The structure of the coatings can be changed by introducing metal atoms into the DLC coatings. Metal atoms can form pure nanocrystalline metals and metal carbides by reacting with carbon atoms, which can be distributed throughout the carbon structure [157]. On the other hand, most metals, including Ti [158], Ag [159] and Zr [160], when incorporated, can shift the G peak to the higher wavenumbers and increase the I_D/I_G ratio. It is explained by an increase in graphite bonds arranged in carbon rings, which demonstrates a decrease in the sp^3/sp^2 ratio caused by the incorporation of metal atoms into the DLC coatings. Wang et al. [161] showed that nanographite and nanocarbides were created in the DLC coatings as a result of the metal incorporation such as titanium. Since Ti–C bonds replaced C–C bonds in the films, the increase in carbon sp^2 C=C and decrease in carbon sp^3 C–C were primarily caused by the presence of TiC.

Although DLC coating shows excellent tribological properties, insufficient coating adhesion as a result of high residual stress is known to be a common limitation for its application. An effective way to overcome this issue is the incorporation of some metal atoms such as Cr [43], Zr [162], Cu [163], Ag [164], Ti [165], and W [166] into the DLC structure to reduce internal stress. The formation of carbides in the carbon network by adding Ti, W, Cr, and Zr improves coating adhesion to the substrate. By doping some other metals such as Ag and Cu into the DLC coating, ductile phases can be formed, improving the toughness of the coating [167]. Ductile phases in the DLC network also increase the coating adhesion to a soft (steel) substrate due to the considerable reduction in residual stress in the coating [168]. The use of metals as dopant, particularly Ti, can reduce the hardness of the tetrahedral amorphous (ta-C) coatings containing a significant amount of sp^3 carbon bonds. Because metal dopants are required to enhance adhesion strength of the coating when ta-C coating is deposited on soft substrates such as steels [169]. In general, the mechanical properties of the DLC coatings are significantly altered by addition of metal atoms, which can be effective in enhancing the tribological characteristics of the coating, as

Fig. 6. a) The friction coefficient and b) wear rate of the double layer N-DLC/DLC and single layer coatings against SiC ball in ambient air [151].

detailed in the following parts.

6.2. Tribological properties of titanium-doped DLC coatings

Titanium is the most common metal used as a dopant into the DLC coatings to increase the durability of industrial parts that are subjected to abrasion. Feng et al. [170] fabricated Ti-doped DLC coatings on AISI 52100 steel. They observed that by adding titanium to the DLC coating, the lubricative properties of the coating can be improved. Bootkul et al. [171] deposited a titanium-doped hydrogenated amorphous carbon coating on a silicon wafer using magnetron sputtering. They showed that even at a lower concentration of titanium, the residual stress and wear resistance of the hydrogenated amorphous carbon coating can be improved, as shown in Fig. 7. Titanium incorporation can decrease the fraction of sp^3 hybridized carbon of the DLC coating, and thus improve the adhesion of the coating to the substrate. Zhou et al. [169] reported that a Ti-DLC coating was deposited on the 304 SS using an unbalanced magnetron sputtering technique. By increasing the titanium concentration from 1.82 wt% to 18.29 wt% in the carbon network, the sp^3 to sp^2 transformation is intensified and nano crystallite titanium carbide can be formed. The most important factor for the improvement of tribological properties in a titanium doped DLC coating is the control of the size and content of the titanium carbide in the carbon network. In other words, a larger and higher concentration of TiC results in higher surface roughness. Consequently, more titanium carbide is involved in the sliding process. This gives rise to a higher friction coefficient and more fluctuation can occur during the wear test [169]. However, the oxygen could not penetrate and destroy the cross-linked carbon network because a diffusion barrier might be created by the TiC-rich surface to prevent oxygen from diffusing into the sublayer. This could improve oxidation resistance of the DLC coatings during the sliding process [172].

Zhao et al. [173] reported that the Ti-DLC coatings fabricated by RF-PECVD showed a low friction coefficient ranging from 0.01 to 0.03 under different loads compared to pure DLC coatings. With a greater friction coefficient (0.05), the pure DLC film fails rapidly. Since the Ti-doped DLC coating is a hard nanocomposite coating made of TiC nanocrystallites dispersed throughout an amorphous carbon matrix, it can prevent microcracks propagation during the sliding test. For tribological applications, such a balance between toughness and hardness is necessary. One of the main elements that can affect the tribological behavior of the DLC coating is the graphitization effect during wear tests [174]. Yetim et al. [175] produced a titanium doped DLC coating with columnar, compact, and dense structure. They demonstrated that a pure

DLC coating is less resistant to wear than a Ti-DLC coating because less micro graphitization occurred during the wear test. By fabricating a composite DLC coating with titanium doping, the environmental adaptability of the coating during the sliding process can be improved so that the rate of micro crack generation is decreased [176].

6.3. Tribological properties of zirconium-doped DLC coatings

Zirconium is one of the metals that can be incorporated into the DLC coating to improve wear resistance. Kumar et al. [177] fabricated Zr incorporated DLC coatings and noticed that a small amount of Zr significantly decreased the wear rate and friction coefficient of the coating. Vitu et al. [178] deposited a Zr-DLC coating by magnetron sputtering and assessed how the tribological properties of the coatings were affected by testing temperatures and relative humidity. They found that variation of contact pressure in the sliding process is inevitable, and therefore it should be considered as part of tribological behavior. Furthermore, they noted that the formation of a Zr-containing tribolayer can influence the friction coefficient, whereas the contact pressure affects the wear rate. Additionally, the Zr-DLC coating showed less susceptibility to the wear test environment compared to the undoped DLC coatings. Wear test conditions and the chemistry of the Zr-DLC coating can influence the structure and composition of the tribolayer. In fact, incorporation of zirconium into the DLC structure can reduce the surface free energy, which can promote the development of a stable tribolayer with low shear on the contact surfaces. Finally, a stable friction coefficient can be achieved by incorporating Zr into the DLC coating due to the lower iron oxide debris particles from the steel ball formed during the wear test compared to the undoped DLC coating [178].

6.4. Tribological properties of tungsten-doped DLC coatings

Other metals, such as tungsten, can be incorporated into the DLC coating to improve the tribological behavior. Gies et al. [179] deposited a W-DLC coating on a steel substrate using a commercial PVD/PECVD technique. Due to the gradual decrease in the tungsten concentration from the top to the substrate interface, the coating exhibits better wear resistance than non-gradient coating [189]. Cao et al. assessed the tribocorrosion behavior of the W-DLC coating fabricated by DC magnetron sputtering on stainless steel substrate. By altering the current of the WC target, the W concentration in the coating changed from 0.9 to 15.1 at. %. Hardness is reduced as the W content in the DLC film increases because W–C bonds are formed, breaking the C–C bonds. The H/E and H^3/E^2 parameters of the DLC (0.94 at% W) coating increased in

Table 3

Tribological behavior and some other characteristics of nitrogen-doped DLC coatings.

Chemical composition/ Microstructure	Deposition technique/ Substrate	Surface roughness (RMS)/thickness (t)	Mechanical Properties	Wear test conditions	Tribological properties	Major Outcome	Ref.
Lower sp^3/sp^2 after N incorporation	PECVD/CoCrMo alloy	t: 0.8 μm RMS: 4.8 nm for highest nitrogen concentration	H: 11.8 GPa E: 142 GPa	Counterpart: UHMPWE Geometry: ball on disk Load: 10 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.11$ $W = 3.11 \times 10^{-5}$ mm^3/Nm For highest nitrogen concentration	Due to increased coating adhesion and decreased roughness of the coatings caused by the addition of nitrogen doping and diamonds, the counter material exhibits significantly lower friction coefficient and wear rates.	[146]
10 at.% of N	PECVD/ Ti-6Al-4V	t: 210 nm	–	Counterpart: steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 1, 5 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.3$ $W = 1.18 \times 10^{-6}$ mm^3/Nm for 10 at.% of N	The “thin ice” phenomenon is the cause of the deterioration in the wear behavior of the coatings at the higher contact load.	[153]
Lower sp^3/sp^2 after N incorporation	PECVD/ Ti-6Al-4V	t: 2 μm for N-DLC	H: 14 GPa E: 115 GPa	Counterpart: steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 5, 15 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.3$ $W = 1.18 \times 10^{-6}$ mm^3/Nm for 10 at.% of N	No notable decrease in friction coefficient was observed in the N-DLC coating, even though the addition of nitrogen to the amorphous hydrogen coating is expected to increase the graphitization.	[154]
11.2 at.% of N/Lower sp^3/sp^2 after N incorporation	magnetron sputtering/Si wafer	t: 0.5–0.9 μm	E: 300 GPa	Counterpart: steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 5 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.1$ $W = 1.18 \times 10^{-6}$ mm^3/Nm for 11.2 at.% of N	The sp^3/sp^2 bonding ratio has an inverse relationship with the friction coefficient of the N-DLC coating.	[136]
0 at.%, 4.4 at.%, 6.2 at. %, and 10.3 at.% of N/Lower sp^3/sp^2 after N incorporation	RF-PECVD/ AISI420 stainless steel and Si (100) wafers	t: 2.6 μm for 6.2 at.% of N	H: 15.2 GPa E: 122 GPa for 6.2 at.% of N	Counterpart: stainless steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 10 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.04$ $W = 9 \times 10^{-8}$ mm^3/Nm for 6.2 at.% of N	The nucleophilic reactivity of the dangling bonds created during sliding can be reduced by the C=N and CN groups acting as potent electron acceptors.	[34]
8.2 at.%, 8.5 at.%, and 9.1 at.% of N	PECVD/AISI 316L stainless steel	t: 2.2 μm , Rz: 3.5 nm for 9.1 at.% of N	H: 3.5 GPa	Counterpart: Al_2O_3 Geometry: ball on disk Load: 10 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.3$ $W = 6 \times 10^{-6}$ mm^3/Nm for 9.1 at.% of N	Nitrogen incorporation in DLC coatings increases the degree of graphitization, which reduces residual stress and hardness but also increases the stability of frictional behavior.	[155]
10 at.%, and 14 at.% of N	Si Wafer/pulsed laser and filtered cathodic arc depositions		H: 15.2 GPa E: 122 GPa for 6.2 at.% of N	Counterpart: SiC Geometry: ball on disk Load: 1 N Environment: Dry & humid	$\mu = 0.3$ $W = 6 \times 10^{-6}$ mm^3/Nm for 10 at.% of N	Incorporating nitrogen into the DLC coatings is a superior option if having minimal wear debris size and polished wear track.	[156]

comparison to undoped DLC coating. These high H/E and H^3/E^2 values could significantly decrease residual stress and increase adhesion strength of the DLC coating. However, the H/E and H^3/E^2 values were reduced as the W content was increased more. The W-DLC coating with lowest W content demonstrated superior corrosion and wear resistance performance in artificial seawater compared to the W-free DLC coating.

6.5. Tribological properties of silver-doped DLC coatings

The impact of silver doping in DLC coating on its tribological properties has been the subject of several studies [180,181]. Basically, by adding soft metals such as Ag, the formed carbide has the potential to function as a lubricant, lowering the friction coefficient [159]. Yu et al. [181] fabricated an Ag-doped DLC coating using multi-ion beam assisted deposition technique. They found that increasing the Ag content from 4.4 to 10.5 % reduced the wear rate and friction coefficient. At a high Ag concentration, low wear resistance and high coefficient of friction were evident. Manninen et al. [182] observed that the tribolayer containing silver on the counterpart formed during the sliding process leads to an

increase in the friction coefficient and wear rate of the Ag-DLC coating with a high silver concentration. Moreover, Ag aggregation on the wear track coupled with a silver-rich transfer layer on the counterpart gives rise to a decrease in wear resistance at high contact pressure. Jing et al. evaluated the tribological properties of the DLC coating with varying concentrations of Ag using high-power pulsed plasma vapor deposition technique. Ag atoms migrate to the worn surface during the friction process, which speeds up the graphitization of the DLC structure. Ag-rich “rod-like wear debris” is produced by the interface with a high graphitized structure, which is more prone to plastic deformation. During the wear test, “Rod-like wear debris” decreases the direct contact between the friction pairs, changing the mode of friction from sliding to rolling [183].

6.6. Tribological properties of chromium-doped DLC coatings

Chromium is another crucial metal used as a dopant in DLC coatings, and it is an excellent choice for an intermediate layer due to its good interaction with carbon atoms [184]. Zou et al. [185] worked on Cr-DLC

Fig. 7. (a) I_D/I_G , (b) hardness, (c) wear track width and (d) critical load of the Ti-DLC coating in different titanium concentrations [171].

coating and showed that residual stress can be reduced from ~ 1 GPa to ~ 0.5 GPa as the Cr concentration increases from 0 at. % to 9.7 at. %. Furthermore, they observed that the pure DLC coating with a high friction coefficient failed during the wear tests at 500°C , whereas the Cr-DLC coating showed a stable friction coefficient. Santiago et al. [186] showed that incorporating chromium into the DLC coating has no significant effect on the carbon sp^3 fraction of the coating. The graphitization of the Cr-DLC coating at high temperatures is delayed significantly compared to non-doped DLC coating. Less brittle nature and more stable tribological behavior at elevated temperatures were achieved by incorporating chromium into the DLC structure.

6.7. Summary

With addition of different types of metal atoms to the DLC coating, some types of carbides can be formed. The size and dispersion of the metal carbides in the carbon network have a significant impact on the tribological behavior of the DLC coating. Generally, some metals, such as titanium and tungsten can reduce internal stress due to the formation of metal carbides, which improve the mechanical properties and wear resistance significantly. By incorporating chromium into the DLC structure, more stable tribological behavior at elevated temperatures can be achieved. The lubricative properties of the DLC coating can be improved by adding titanium to it, allowing it to serve as a solid lubricant for space and vacuum applications. For use in bio-tribological applications such as hip joints, titanium-doped DLC coating is a great choice. Some of the metal dopants used in DLC coatings produced using various techniques are summarized in Table 4. Their tribological behavior, chemical composition, and mechanical properties are also reported.

7. Multi-doped DLC coating

7.1. Mechanical and tribological properties

Multi-doped DLC coating is an excellent choice for combining the

desired properties of the elements to improve tribological behavior. Therefore, the accurate selection of elements in multi-doped DLC coating can be very crucial. Dai et al. [192] fabricated (Al, Cr, Si)-DLC coatings using the hybrid ion beam system. Hard Cr-C carbide could restore hardness, and the addition of Al atoms can significantly reduce internal stress of the coating. Si atoms could form a bond with $\text{sp}^2\text{-C}$ which can maintain the sp^3 -hybridized bond structure. It is crucial for enhancing the thermal stability of the coating because the graphitization temperature of the DLC coating increases over 500°C . Moreover, the (Al, Cr, Si)-DLC coatings demonstrated exceptional tribological performance with a low friction coefficient (0.05) and wear rate, along with relatively low residual stress in addition to their great thermal stability. Wang et al. [193] studied the influence of nitrogen and silicon co-doping on the tribological and mechanical properties of the DLC coatings at elevated temperatures. They confirmed the Si-C, Si-N and C-N bonding are stable thermodynamically in the (Si, N)-DLC coatings which can enhance thermal stability and oxidation resistant of the coating at high temperature. The transfer layer formed during the wear test had a high degree of flexibility and deformation capacity. Because the (Si, N) DLC coating has an amorphous carbon network with fullerene-like nanostructure and the shear-induced stacking structure which can reduce the friction coefficient (0.1) significantly over 500°C . In another study, the (F, Si) hydrogenated DLC coating was deposited using PECVD technique. It showed that more $\text{sp}^3\text{-C}$ content forms as a result of the doping of the Si atom, whereas a little rise in $\text{sp}^2\text{-C}$ clusters can occur due to the fluorine doping. Moreover, the hardness of the coating is decreased by doping Si and F elements, due to the increase of the carbon structural disorder of the coating. The (F, Si) hydrogenated DLC coating displayed a low friction coefficient, which is explained by formation of silicon-rich oxide debris and the high hydrogen content as a result of the Si doping [106]. In another work, Wei et al. et al. [194] fabricated a novel (F, Si) hydrogenated DLC coating using combining plasma immersion implantation and hollow cathode discharge. They demonstrated stable superhydrophobic coating, which is highly useful for lowering the friction coefficient at high relative humidity conditions. All in all, it is believed that one of the best approaches to enhance the tribological

Table 4
Tribological behavior and some other characteristics of metal-doped DLC coatings.

Chemical composition/ Microstructure	Deposition technique/ Substrate	Surface roughness/ thickness (t)	Mechanical Properties	Wear test conditions	Tribological properties	Major Outcome	Ref.
W-DLC	magnetron sputtering/HNBR (hydrogenated nitrile butadiene) rubber sheet	t: 1 μm	–	Counterpart: steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 1 N Environment: dry & humid	$\mu = 0.2$	After tribotest, hardly any wear was seen on the wear tracks because of high elastic modulus of HNBR rubber.	[187]
Ni-DLC	Magnetron Sputtering Deposition/Silicon	t: 165 nm Ra: 0.6 nm	H: 24 GPa E: 192.2 GPa	Counterpart: steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 3 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.17$ $W = 1.6 \times 10^{-17}$ mm^3/Nm	The wear resistance of the Ni-DLC films was significantly reduced by an increase in Ni content because it damaged the sp ³ -bonded cross-linking structures.	[194]
Cr-DLC/3 at.%, 4.8 at.%, 7.2 at.%, and 9.7 at.% of Cr	Magnetron Sputtering/Stainless Steel	t: 4 μm for 4.8 at.% of Cr		Counterpart: A 319 Al Geometry: ball on disk Load: 5 N Environment: dry and different temperature	$\mu = 0.17$ $W = 1.6 \times 10^{-17}$ mm^3/Nm	Transfer layers with inadequate passivation were formed as a result of water evaporation, seriously damaging the coating.	[188]
Cr-DLC/3 at.%, 9 at.%, and 20 at.% of Cr/ Lower sp ³ /sp ² after Cr incorporation	high power impulse magnetron sputtering (HiPIMS)/Stainless Steel	t: 1 μm Ra: 6 nm For 3 at.% of Cr	H: 29.2 GPa E: 236 GPa For 3 at.% of Cr	Counterpart: Al ₂ O ₃ Geometry: ball on disk Load: 1, 5 N Environment: dry and different temperature	$\mu = 0.11$ $W = 5 \times 10^{-16}$ mm^3/Nm	Due to the incorporation of small amount of Cr (up to 3 at.%) into the DLC coating the graphitization mechanism is delayed at high temperatures.	[189]
Ti-DLC/19 at.% of Ti	PECVD/ Hydrogenated acrylonitrile butadiene rubber & Si wafer	t: 1.10 μm	H: 13 GPa	Counterpart: steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 1, 3 N Environment: dry and humid	$\mu = 0.15$	The high friction coefficient at low load is caused by inadequate peak stress on the coated rubber's asperities to increase surface graphitization.	[190]
W-DLC & Ti-DLC	PECVD/ Hydrogenated acrylonitrile butadiene rubber/	t: 300 nm	–	Counterpart: steel Geometry: ball on disk Load: 3 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.21$ for Ti-DLC & $\mu = 0.22$ for W-DLC	The existence of cracks in the coating has no impact on the frictional properties of the coating if the interfacial adhesion is strong enough to avoid delamination.	[191]
Ag-DLC/0 at.%, 0.4 at.%, 2.41 at.% and 2.99 at.% of Ag	magnetron sputtering/Si wafer	t: 540 nm for 2.99 at.% of Ag	H: 13.3 GPa	Counterpart: Al ₂ O ₃ Geometry: ball on disk Load: 1 N Environment: dry	$\mu = 0.16$ $W = 14 \times 10^{-17}$ mm^3/Nm for 2.99 at.% of Ag	Higher Ag concentration causes the formation of rod-like wear debris during wear tests, which shifts the friction mechanism from sliding to rolling.	[183]

properties of DLC coatings is by multi-doping combined with appropriate element selection and content.

8. Conclusion

This review provides a comprehensive survey on how different dopants can influence the tribological behavior of diamond-like carbon coatings. With precise design of the DLC coating, and by carefully selecting the desired element, an excellent combination of low friction and superior wear resistance can be achieved. Among different types of deposition methods, PECVD and PVD have frequently been applied for deposition of doped diamond like carbon coatings. Applying various types of techniques and adjusting the process parameters can change the sp²/sp³ ratios in the DLC coatings. This crucial factor is the main concept for using different elements as dopants, such as N, F, Si, Cr, and Ti, to improve the tribological and mechanical properties of DLC coatings.

However, the requirement to find an appropriate correlation between the types or amounts of the incorporated elements and the tribological properties of the DLC coating is the most critical issue. Indeed, some dopants, such as nitrogen, can decrease the hardness of the DLC coatings, whereas silicon can increase the hardness of the coating. A desired balance between toughness and hardness of the DLC coating is

essential to obtain a high adhesion strength so that tribological behavior can be considerably improved. Regardless of the types and content of dopants, some other parameters, such as temperature, substrate, target, arc current, and surface treatment process can undoubtedly influence the wear rate and friction coefficient. With respect to the recent advancements in technologies for the deposition process, the reproducibility of doped-DLC coatings has been markedly improved. Therefore, they have a great potential for production in large-scale applications in the close future.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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